

Discussion of Probability of Presence Versus $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ in Quantum Mechanics

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In (1), a paper entitled, Probability of Presence Versus $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$, (where $W(x,t)$ is the quantum wavefunction), it is argued that $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ is not really the probability of presence as stated in textbooks. An important statement is made in the abstract: "In particular, zeroes of the wavefunction do not indicate vanishing probability density of presence." (1) The approach of (1) is to argue that a correct probability of presence is given nonrelativistically by $W^*(x,t)W(x,t) + a \text{ grad}W^* \cdot \text{grad}W$, which is the nonrelativistic limit of Dirac's relativistic Wd (dagger) Wd , where Wd is a 4-component spinor. "a" is linked to v/c which is small non-relativistically, but (1) argues that $\text{grad}W$ may be high in some cases.

We argue, as we have before, that $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ in bound systems shows spatial resolution, not necessarily probability of presence. Furthermore, it allows for W_n 's to be orthogonal in space. In particular, a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ has resolution \hbar/p , but $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. Thus, resolution and orthogonality and probability of presence are different things. Given the complex form of $\exp(ipx)$, a zero of $\cos(px)$ is not a zero of $\sin(px)$, but these zeros do define resolution and this is experimentally observed in two slit interference. Furthermore, $W = \exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2)$ for two slit interference, used in W^*W does seem to reproduce the interference pattern which does have zero points which match experimental results.

For a bound state, however, one uses time averaging, i.e. $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and $a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ are added even though they occur at different times, especially for high energy levels which should approach classical physics. This approach serves to show the resolution in x occurring in the bound state, but the zero points of $W(x)$ do not necessarily represent zero probability of presence because for high energy levels, the particle should move to the right for some time and then to the left for a mutually exclusive other time. A complex wavefunction: Sum over $p > 0$ $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ describes motion to the right and given the complex nature, one does not have zeros of presence. The real part might have a zero, but the complex part is not 0 at the same point, we argue. Thus, zeros of $W^*(x)W(x)$, at least in the bound case scenario, do not represent zeros of presence, as we have suggested in previous notes. As a result, the correction $a \text{ grad}W^* \cdot \text{grad}W$ may apply, as argued in (1), but W^*W not representing probability of presence, at least in bound states, seems to already occur for a different reason, we suggest.

Probability of Presence Versus $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$

Standard textbooks state that $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$, where $W(x,t)$ is the quantum wavefunction, represents the probability of presence, meaning that zero points of W^*W indicate the absence of the particle at certain x points, which is difficult to picture physically.

In the abstract of (1) is stated that: "In particular, zeroes of the wavefunction do not indicate vanishing probability density of presence."

The approach of (1), however, is to use the Dirac probability Wd (dagger) Wd , where Wd is a 4-component spinor. The nonrelativistic limit is:

| W |

$$|\sigma \cdot p/2m W| \quad ((1))$$

Here σ represents Pauli matrices. This leads to:

$$W^*W + 1/4m \text{grad}W^* \cdot \text{grad}W \quad ((2))$$

The correction term is of the order of v/c . Nonrelativistically, this should be small, but (1) argues that nevertheless it may make zeros of W^*W , nonzero. For W real, $\text{grad}W \cdot \text{grad}W$ should be positive and zeros of $\text{grad}W$ only occur at peaks or troughs and so one cannot have $W=0$ and $\text{grad}W=0$ at the same point. Thus, there are no true zeros of expression ((2)), at least for W real. It is also argued that there are cases for which the second term in ((2)) is large.

Resolution

We wish to suggest a different argument, which we have mentioned in previous notes. We argue that the zeros which are linked to a wavefunction really represent resolution. For example, $\exp(ipx)$ has a resolution of \hbar/p in x , but $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)=1$. The density does not show any zeros, nevertheless the resolution in x is key for 2-slit interference etc. Furthermore, adding $\exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2)$ where r_1 and r_2 are distance vectors from the center of each slit to the same point on a far away screen, leads to a pattern which does have zeros. Thus, the zeros in W^*W are experimentally relevant in this case, it seems.

Bound States

The quantum approach for bound states is to average over time, it seems, because $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are included in the wavefunction, i.e.

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((3))$$

As a result, one may see crests and troughs, but we argue that these represent x resolution, not probability of presence. One must have zeros in order to have the wavefunction switch from positive to negative values. This sign switching is required because different $W_n(x)$ must be orthogonal over x and this cannot occur for $W_n(x) > 0$ for all x . In other words, the resolution of $\exp(ipx)$ is linked to momentum conservation and that of $W_n(x)$, real for bound states, to energy state orthogonality.

Orthogonality considerations, however, are not the same as probability of presence. In the case of a bound state, the average over time leads to zeros in $W(x)$, but physically such an averaging is not occurring if one considers probability of presence. Classically, a bound particle moves to the right and then to the left and the same applies to quantum mechanics, especially for higher energy levels. This means that $W(x)$ is a time average and its zeros correspond to this average, not to probability of presence. In other words, if a bound particle is moving forward, then:

$$\text{Sum over } p > 0 \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

applies. This is a complex, not real term, and when multiplied by its complex conjugate does not have zeros, just as $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ does not have zeros. Thus we suggest that the zeros of W^*W for a bound state apply to x resolution, not probability of presence.

Classical Limit

The concept of time averaging, i.e. including $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ together in a sum, occurs for all energy levels in quantum mechanics. At high energy levels, however, one must see classical physics appear, i.e. resolutions in x are sharp. Classical physics shows experimentally that a particle moves to the right and then to the left (in a bound state) and so one must note that quantum time averaging is used to show resolution and not probability of presence.

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) suggests that W^*W (nonrelativistic) does not represent probability of presence. (1) takes a Dirac 4-spinor in $W^\dagger W$ and converts it to a nonrelativistic result: $W^*W + a \text{grad}W^* \cdot \text{grad}W$. (1) argues that the second term, which is of the order of v/c , removes zeros of W^*W .

We suggest that for a bound state, zeros of W^*W appear because one uses time averaging, i.e. includes $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and $a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ together in a sum. In terms of presence, however, this does not happen, especially for higher energy levels because a particle moves to the right and then to the left. A high energy quantum picture should be consistent with classical physics and time averaging appears for all energy levels in quantum mechanics. Rather, this time averaging approach is needed to show the spatial resolution which exists and to make W_n 's orthogonal. In terms of probability of presence, a particle is either moving to the right or to the left. If it is moving to the right, then it is represented by $\sum_{p>0} a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and this is complex and so has no zeros. As a result, we argue that the zeros of W^*W for a bound state do not represent zeros of probability of presence even without the correction term $a \text{grad}W^* \cdot \text{grad}W$.

References

1. Wilczek, F. and Yi, Z. Probability of Presence Versus $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ May 8, 2024
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/4901b86d6adc4967fbed8a9556359a6832b48d3>